

Article title: The Paradox of Oily Malnourished Skin

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The Paradox of Oily Malnourished Skin

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ABSTRACT

Oily skin (seborrhea) is a common cosmetic problem that occurs when oversized sebaceous glands produce excessive amounts of sebum giving the appearance of shiny and greasy skin. Oily skin is at the same time malnourished because excessive amounts of sebum wash out the protective and hydrating skin factors, such as natural moisturizing factor, and therefore dual treatment is necessary, which consists of meticulous cleaning of the excessive sebum and profound nourishment of the skin. Skin microcirculation plays a significant role in the skin homeostasis. Dermal venules are important for waste removal from the skin, whilst dermal arterioles are important for the transportation of gases and nutrients towards the skin. Improvement of the skin microcirculation might be a useful tool in the maintenance of healthy skin and additional treatment for oily skin, acne, accelerated aging and wrinkles. Demodicosis causes the vicious circle of the oily skin: excessive amounts of sebum lead to more severe demodicosis, which then aggravates acne and increases the production of the sebum.

Keywords: paradox; malnourished; oily; skin; demodex; microcirculation

INTRODUCTION

Oily skin (seborrhea) is a common cosmetic problem that occurs when oversized sebaceous glands produce excessive amounts of sebum giving the appearance of shiny and greasy skin¹. Natural moisturizing factor (NMF) is essential for appropriate stratum corneum hydration, barrier homeostasis, desquamation and plasticity. It is formed from filaggrin proteolysis to small, hygroscopic molecules including amino acids².

Greasy skin is usually treated with different

kinds of cleansing preparations. Excessive cleaning of the greasy skin without consequent hydration and nourishment can wash out the NMF, leaving the skin dehydrated and malnourished.

DUAL TREATMENT

Oily skin requires dual treatment. First step is meticulous cleaning of the excessive sebum. There are numerous cosmetic, cosmeceutical products and local medications that can be used for the cleaning process, such as micellar water, micellar shampoo for greasy

hair, various types of skin masks labeled for the oily/greasy skin (with active charcoal, salicylic acid, natural mud...), creams for acne with zinc and other. Second step is profound nourishment and hydration therapy. Examples are nourishing creams, usually labeled for dry and very dry skin, like vitamin creams (with A, C and/or E vitamin), almond oil with vitamin E, various types of hydrating creams and face moisturizers.

Important factor in the nourishment of the skin and hair is healthy balanced diet and skin, nails and hair vitamin complex dietary supplements if dietary vitamin intake is not adequate.

SKIN MICROCIRCULATION

Skin microcirculation is located in the dermis and hypodermis layers. It plays a significant role in skin homeostasis (transportation of gases, nutrients, waste, hormones), in body thermoregulation, in blood pressure regulation and in inflammatory response. Dermal arterioles and venules are composed of endothelial cells, connective tissues (collagen, elastin) and smooth muscle cells which allow vessel vasoconstriction and vasodilation. Dermal capillaries are composed of a single layer of endothelial cells and of pericytes surrounded by a basal membrane. A microcirculation dysfunction due to external factors (sun exposure, heat, cold, microorganisms and food) or internal factors (immune system) can cause redness, venous

insufficiency or rosacea. Microcirculation is also altered by skin ageing, with a progressive decrease of new blood vessel formation (angiogenesis). This age-related alteration of skin microcirculation may have different consequences: sensation of cold, pallor, cutaneous ischemia, alopecia³.

Skin microcirculation hypofunction/dysfunction might play a significant role in the development of some skin diseases, such as acne and seborrhea. Dermal venules are important for waste removal from the skin, whilst dermal arterioles are important for the transportation of gases and nutrients towards the skin. Microcirculation hypofunction might be associated with accumulation of toxins and waste, including excessive sebum, which might contribute to the development of seborrhea and acne. Microcirculation is also altered by skin ageing, with a progressive decrease of new blood vessel formation. Poor skin microcirculation might be also associated with accelerated aging of the skin and development of the wrinkles because gases and nutrients are poorly transported by dysfunctional dermal arterioles.

Improvement of the skin microcirculation might be a useful tool in the maintenance of healthy skin and additional treatment for oily skin, acne, accelerated skin ageing and wrinkles. Skin microcirculation can be improved with skin massage: manual skin

massage, skin brush, T-Sonic™ facial cleansing brush and anti-aging system Luna, and similar devices. Skin microcirculation is also improved with healthy and balanced diet.

Jarnert and coworkers found in the study that glycaemic normalization improved skin microcirculation in patients with type 2 diabetes with mild cardiovascular engagement⁴.

DEMODICOSIS

Demodex is a genus of tiny mites that live in or near hair follicles of mammals⁵. Two species live on humans: *Demodex folliculorum* and *Demodex brevis*, both frequently referred to as eyelash mites. *D. folliculorum* is found in hair follicles, while *D. brevis* lives in sebaceous glands connected to hair follicles. Both species are primarily found in the face, near the nose, the eyelashes, and eyebrows, but also occur elsewhere on the body⁶. *Demodex* were considered commensals, but are now considered parasitic. However, in the vast majority of cases the mites go unobserved without any adverse symptoms, though in certain cases (usually related to a suppressed immune system, caused by stress or illness), mite populations can dramatically increase. This results in a condition known as **demodicosis** or *Demodex* mite bite,

characterized by itching, inflammation, and other skin disorders. Blepharitis (inflammation of the eyelids) can be also caused by *Demodex* mites^{7, 8}.

Demodex has been associated with the development of *pityriasis folliculorum*, rosacea, perioral dermatitis, seborrheic dermatitis, pustular eruption, blepharitis, seborrheic alopecia, the dermatosis that persists and shows a resistance to classical therapies, and acne⁹⁻¹⁹.

DEMODICOSIS AND ACNE

Post adolescent acne are generally mild to moderate in severity and presents with more inflammatory lesions and fewer comedones when compared to adolescent acne. Hormonal parameters are normal in a majority of patients. Several environmental factors are emphasized, including stress, environmental pollution, ultraviolet exposure and smoking. Emotional stress is suggested to increase adrenal androgens, causing sebaceous hyperplasia, and may play a role in the etiopathogenesis of acne²⁰⁻²³. A growing number of case reports and epidemiological studies show that *Demodex* has an aetiopathogenic role in acne vulgaris¹⁷ because mites can easily become pathogenic²⁴.

The causal relationship of *Demodex* mites in skin lesions has been suspected to occur through several mechanisms. The mites may

mechanically block the follicles, leading to distension and causing intra-follicular hyperkeratosis^{17, 25}. The mites can migrate from one follicle to another at a speed of 8–16 mm over 7 h. The female mites are thought to deposit their ova in the deeper areas of the pilosebaceous unit, where the young will be able to continue their lifestyle to the adult form²⁴. The mite body is covered with a hard exoskeleton and the presence of the mite's chitinous external skeleton may act like a foreign body and contribute to the formation of granulomas. Most probably, when *Demodex* mites breach the epithelial barrier, their antigens influence the immune system of the host and induce a type IV hypersensitivity reaction. The waste products of *Demodex* mites and/or associated bacteria may activate the elements of the innate immune system or stimulate the immune system through the mechanism of delayed hypersensitivity

reaction, and this hypersensitivity reaction may be the triggering factor for acne development²⁵.

Patients with mixed, oily or dry skin were more likely to be infested with *Demodex* when compared with patients with neutral skin²⁶. Most of acne patients had oily or mixed skin type²⁷ and they could be readily infested with *Demodex*²⁶. Dokuyucu and coworkers reported that *Demodex* positivity was significantly higher in obese patients²⁸. Some authors suggested that poor blood glucose regulation, obesity and metabolic syndrome all increase the susceptibility to *D. folliculorum* mite infestation²⁸⁻³². There is a suggestion that acne aetiology, and especially post adolescent acne, is triggered by insulin resistance³³.

When regular treatments for acne vulgaris are ineffective, examination for *Demodex* mites and therapy for *Demodex* should be considered³⁴.

CONCLUSIONS

Oily skin is paradoxically malnourished, and dual treatment is necessary, which consists of the meticulous cleaning of the excessive sebum on the one hand, and profound nourishment and hydration on the other hand. Improvement of the skin microcirculation might also be a very useful tool in the maintenance of healthy skin and additional treatment for oily skin, acne, accelerated skin ageing and wrinkles. In the treatment of acne vulgaris, rosacea, seborrheic dermatitis and other dermatoses resistant to classical therapies, topical antiparasitic agents might be a successful treatment. These substances are crotamiton, ivermectin, metronidazole and permethrin. Creams, unguents and face gels, with one of these antiparasitic agents in combination with substances that regulate sebum secretion (sabal), kerato-regulators and keratolytics (guanidine glycolate, Keluamid®), antibacterial and

antifungal agents (zinc oxide, salicylic acid, selenium sulfide, sulfur, piroctone olamine), might be beneficial for patients with various skin diseases that are associated with demodicosis, especially for acne vulgaris and seborrheic dermatitis. Demodicosis causes the vicious circle of the oily skin: excessive amounts of sebum lead to more severe demodicosis, which then aggravates acne and increases the production of the sebum. Therefore, timely diagnosis and treatment of demodicosis in patients with oily skin and acne is crucial.

REFERENCES

1. Sakuma TH, Maibach HI. Oily skin: an overview. *Skin Pharmacol Physiol.* 2012;25(5):227-35.
2. Robinson M, Visscher M, Laruffa A, Wickett R. Natural moisturizing factors (NMF) in the stratum corneum (SC). I. Effects of lipid extraction and soaking. *J Cosmet Sci.* 2010;61(1):13-22.
3. SKIN MICROCIRCULATION & VASCULARIZATION.
<https://www.bioalternatives.com/en/cosmetic-claims/skin-microcirculation-vascularization/>
access date 04.01.2022.
4. Jarnert C, Kalani M, Rydén L, Böhm F. Strict glycaemic control improves skin microcirculation in patients with type 2 diabetes: a report from the Diabetes mellitus And Diastolic Dysfunction (DADD) study. *Diab Vasc Dis Res.* 2012;9(4):287-95.
5. Yong E. Everything you never wanted to know about the mites that eat, crawl, and have sex on your face. Not Exactly Rocket Science. *Discover.* 2012.
6. Rufli T, Mumcuoglu Y. The hair follicle mites *Demodex folliculorum* and *Demodex brevis*: biology and medical importance. A review. *Dermatologica.* 1981;162(1):1-11.
7. Marcinowska Z, Kosik-Bogacka D, Lanocha-Arendarczyk N, Czepita D, Lanocha A. Demodex folliculorum and demodex brevis. *Pomeranian J Life Sci.* 2015;61(1):108-14.
8. Lindsey K, Matsumara S, Hatel E, Akpek EK. Interventions for chronic blepharitis. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2012;5:CD00556.
9. Turgut Erdemir A, Gurel MS, Koku Aksu AE, Falay T, Inan Yuksel E, Sarikaya E. Demodex mites in acne rosacea: reflectance confocal microscopic study. *Australas J Dermatol.* 2017;58(2):e26-e30.
10. Firat PY, Geçit İ, Depecik F, Karadan M, Karci E, Karaman Ü, Çalik S. Demodex spp. positivity among laboratory staff, kitchen staff, cleaning workers and nurses working in a state hospital]. *Turkiye Parazitol Derg.* 2010;34(4):164-7.
11. Casas C, Paul C, Lahfa M, Livideanu B, Lejeune O, Alvarez-Georges S, et al. Quantification of Demodex folliculorum by PCR in rosacea and its relationship to skin innate immune activation. *Exp Dermatol.* 2012;21(12):906-10.
12. Dolenc-Voljc M, Pohar M, Lunder T. Density of *Demodex folliculorum* in perioral dermatitis.

- Acta Derm Venereol.* 2005;85:211-5
13. Karıncaoglu Y, Tepe B, Kalayci B, Atambay M, Seyhan M. Is *Demodex folliculorum* an aetiological factor in seborrhoeic dermatitis? *Clin Exp Dermatol.* 2009;34(8):e516-20.
 14. Helou W, Avitan-Hersh E, Bergman R. *Demodex folliculitis* of the scalp: clinicopathological study of an uncommon entity. *Am J Dermatopathol.* 2016;38:658-63.
 15. Kabataş N, Doğan AŞ, Kabataş EU, Acar M, Biçer T, Gürdal C. The Effect of *Demodex* Infestation on Blepharitis and the Ocular Symptoms. *Eye Contact Lens.* 2017;43(1):64-67.
 16. Türk M, Oztürk I, Sener AG, Küçükbay S, Afşar I, Maden A. Comparison of incidence of *Demodex folliculorum* on the eyelash follicule in normal people and blepharitis patients. *Türkiye Parazitoloj Derg.* 2007;31(4):296-7.
 17. Zhao YE, Hu L, Wu LP, Ma JX. A meta-analysis of association between acne vulgaris and *Demodex* infestation. *J Zhejiang Univ Sci B.* 2012;13:192-202.
 18. Khodaeiani E, Fouladi RF, Yousefi N, Amirnia M, Babaeinejad S, Shokri J. Efficacy of 2% metronidazole gel in moderate acne vulgaris. *Indian J Dermatol.* 2012;57(4):279-81.
 19. Baysal V, Aydemir M, Yorgancıgil B, Yıldırım M. Akne vulgaris etyopatogenezinde *D. folliculorum*'ların rolünün araştırılması. *Türkiye Parazitoloj Derg.* 1997;21:265-8.
 20. Kucharska A, Szmurło A, Sińska B. Significance of diet in treated and untreated acne vulgaris. *Adv Dermatol Allergol.* 2016;33:81-6.
 21. Romańska-Gocka K, Woźniak M, Kaczmarek-Skamira E, Zegarska B. The possible role of diet in the pathogenesis of adult female acne. *Adv Dermatol Allergol.* 2016;33:416-42.
 22. Khunger N, Kumar C. A clinico-epidemiological study of adult acne: is it different from adolescent acne? *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol.* 2012;78:335-41.
 23. Goulden V, Clark SM, Cunliffe WJ. Post-adolescent acne: a review of clinical features. *Br J Dermatol.* 1997;136:66-70.
 24. Lacey N, Russell-Hallinan A, Powell FC. Study of *Demodex* mites. Challenges and solutions. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol.* 2016;30:764-75,
 25. Lacey N, Ni Raghallaigh S, Powell FC. *Demodex* mites: commensals, parasites or mutualistic organisms? *Dermatology.* 2011;222:128-30
 26. Zhao YE, Guo N, Xun M, Xu JR, Wang M, Wang DL. Sociodemographic characteristics and risk factor analysis of *Demodex* infestation (Acari: Demodicidae). *J Zhejiang Univ Sci B.* 2011;12(12):998-1007.
 27. Zaenglein AL, Pathy AL, Schlosser BJ, Alikhan A, Baldwin HE, Berson DS, et al. Guidelines of care for the management of acne vulgaris. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2016;74(5):945-73.e33.
 28. Dokuyucu R, Kaya OA, Yula E, Ustun I, Bayram F, Gokce C. The Presence of *Demodex Folliculorum* in Various Obese Groups According to BMI Levels. *Arch Iran Med.*

- 2016;19(3):210-4.
29. Gökçe C, Aycan-Kaya Ö, Yula E, Üstün I, Yengil E, Sefil F, et al. The effect of blood glucose regulation on the presence of opportunistic *Demodex folliculorum* mites in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *J Int Med Res*. 2013;41(5):1752-8.
30. Keskin Kurt R, Aycan Kaya O, Karateke A, Silfeler DB, Soylu Karapınar O, Akkoca AN, Hakverdi AU. Increased density of *Demodex folliculorum* mites in pregnancies with gestational diabetes. *Med Princ Pract*. 2014;23(4):369-72.
31. Yamashita LS, Cariello AJ, Geha NM, Yu MC, Hofling-Lima AL. *Demodex folliculorum* on the eyelash follicle of diabetic patients. *Arq Bras Oftalmol*. 2011;74(6):422-4.
32. Enginyurt O, Karaman U, Cetin F, Ozer A. The prevalence of *Demodex* species and its relationship with the metabolic syndrome in women of Malatya Province, Turkey. *Jundishapur J Microbiol*. 2015;8:24322.
33. Çerman AA, Aktaş E, Altunay İK, Arıcı JE, Tulunay A, Oztürk FY. Dietary glyceemic factors, insulin resistance, and adiponectin levels in acne vulgaris. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2016;75(1):155-62.
34. Akçınar UG, Ünal E, Doğruman AI F. *Demodex* spp. as a possible aetiopathogenic factor of acne and relation with acne severity and type. *Postepy Dermatol Alergol*. 2018;35(2):174-181.